

GOITRE IS A GROUP OF DISEASES CHARACTERIZED BY ENLARGEMENT OF THE THYROID GLAND

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Abstract. According to the World Health Organization, more than 665 million people worldwide suffer from endemic goiter and other thyroid diseases. And 1.5 billion people are at risk of developing iodine deficiency diseases. Among these diseases, tuberculosis is becoming an urgent issue for most countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, in recent years.

Key words: Thyroid gland, Chronic iodine deficiency, causes, symptoms, treatment, prevention.

ЗОБ – ГРУППА ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ, ХАРАКТЕРИЗУЮЩИХСЯ УВЕЛИЧЕНИЕМ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ.

Аннотация. По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения, более 665 миллионов человек во всем мире страдают эндемическим зобом и другими заболеваниями щитовидной железы. А 1,5 миллиарда человек подвержены риску развития заболеваний, вызванных дефицитом йода. Среди этих заболеваний в последние годы актуальной проблемой для большинства стран мира, в том числе и для Узбекистана, становится туберкулез.

Ключевые слова: Щитовидная железа, Хронический йододефицит, причины, симптомы, лечение, профилактика.

In the front part of the human neck, there is a thyroid gland, which is shaped like a butterfly, and this organ plays an important role in the functioning of the nervous system, digestion, bone tissue and metabolism.

The thyroid gland secretes 3 different hormones, which ensure the normal growth, maturation, and development of the body, and support the normal functioning of organs such as the stomach and intestines. If there are problems in the synthesis of any of them, this will lead to serious diseases in the human body.

Goitre is an enlargement of this gland (normally the weight of the thyroid gland is 20-30 grams) and the disease is mainly caused by lack of iodine. Iodine deficiency can be caused by a person's lifestyle, diet, stress, environmental conditions, and several other factors.

When there is a deficiency of iodine in the human body, the thyroid gland sends a small amount of iodine to the cells. As a result, the synthesis of hormones decreases, and the body acts through the pituitary gland to balance this process. As a result, the thyroid gland enlarges and goiter develops.

Chronic iodine deficiency and thyroid dysfunction cause mental retardation, depression, dry skin, hair loss, constipation, diarrhea, infertility, decreased sexual activity, changes in bone development, short stature, and diseases such as osteoporosis, hypertension, and atherosclerosis.

diffuse (uniform enlargement of the thyroid gland);

nodular (nodule formation in thyroid tissue);

cystic (formation of cysts in the thyroid gland);

diffuse toxic (Bazedova's disease);

mixed. (total enlargement of the thyroid gland forming a nodule)

Reasons

The disease occurs as a result of the failure of the thyroid gland and changes in its size.

Reasons:

hereditary factor;

lack of iodine in the body;

adenoma, thyroid cancer;

insufficient or excessive production of thyroid hormones (hyperthyroidism);

decreased immunity;

diseases of internal organs.

Signs

Symptoms characteristic of goiter:

enlargement of the thyroid gland;

enlarged eyes;

weakness;

profuse sweating;

rapid weight loss;

increased blood pressure;

throat disease;

a feeling of fullness in the throat;

pains in the chest area;

shortness of breath, difficulty swallowing.

In cases where the goiter is small (up to 3 cm), signs may not be noticeable.

If you find that you have similar symptoms, contact your doctor immediately. It is easier to prevent the consequences of the disease than to eliminate it.

Diagnostics

To determine how to treat goiter, the endocrinologist conducts the following studies and tests:

general blood analysis;

urinalysis;

immunogram;

ultrasound examination of the thyroid gland;

thyroid biopsy;

thyroid scintigraphy.

Treatment

Treatment of goitre includes:

drugs that inhibit the formation of thyroid hormones;

preparations containing radioactive iodine;

anti-measles drugs;

surgery.

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Diet

During treatment, patients should eat foods rich in iodine:

fish;

vegetables (carrots, tomatoes, beets);

fruit (pineapple, grape, apple);

beef;

butter, milk;

egg

Dangerous aspects

If thyroid treatment is not started on time, the following complications may develop:

circulatory disorders;

pressure on esophagus, trachea;

acute inflammation of the thyroid gland;

benign growths in the groin area.

Risk group

The risk group includes:

people with a genetic predisposition;

people with autoimmune diseases;

people exposed to radiation in the area of the thyroid gland.

people with adenoma or thyroid cancer;

Prevention

It is recommended to prevent:

eating foods rich in iodine;

avoid staying in the sun for a long time, avoiding radiation;

Physiotherapy in the area of the thyroid gland (magnetolaserotherapy).

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